

SARAS CALL h2020-ICT-2016-2017
INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

SARAS

"Smart Autonomous Robotic Assistant Surgeon"

D1.2 – Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform

Due date of deliverable: December 31st, 2018

Actual submission date: June 30th, 2019

Grant agreement number: 779813

Lead contractor: Università di Verona

Start date of project: 01/01/2018

Duration: 36 months

Project funded by the European Commission within the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation HORIZON 2020	
Dissemination Level	
PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web	✓
CO = Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement	
CI = Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.	
Int = Internal Working Document	

D1.2- Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform

Editors

Elettra Oleari (OSR)

Alice Leporini (OSR)

Diana Trojanniello (OSR)

Alessia Cristiano (FCSR)

Contributors

Riccardo Muradore (UNIVR)

Francesco Setti (UNIVR)

Version	Date	Description
1.0	31-12-2018	First submission to Participant Portal
2.0	01-04-2019	Second version (still preliminary)
3.0	30-06-2019	Final submission to Participant Portal

The work described in this document has been conducted within the project SARAS, started in January 2018. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No.779813

Table of Contents

List of acronyms	4
List of Tables	5
List of Figures.....	6
1 Executive summary	7
2 Introduction	8
2.1 <i>Purpose and structure of the document</i>	8
3 SARAS MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform functional test plan	9
3.1 <i>SARAS surgical task-oriented tests</i>	9
3.2 <i>SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform Qualitative Assessment Questionnaire</i>	10
3.3 <i>SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform Usability Questionnaire</i>	10
3.4 <i>SARAS Communication and Coordination Questionnaires</i>	11
4 Description of the SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform pre-tests	12
4.1 <i>Minutes of first SARAS meeting (22nd January 2019)</i>	13
4.2 <i>Minutes of second SARAS meeting (15th February 2019)</i>	14
4.3 <i>Minutes of third SARAS meeting (27th February 2019)</i>	15
5 Functional evaluation of the SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform	16
5.1 <i>Results of the first evaluation - 17th May 2019</i>	19
5.2 <i>Results of the second evaluation - 31st May 2019</i>	20
5.3 <i>Results of the third evaluation - 19th June 2019</i>	26
6 Discussion on the results obtained	30
6.1 <i>Qualitative Assessment Questionnaire</i>	30
6.2 <i>Usability Survey</i>	30
6.3 <i>Communication and Coordination Questionnaires</i>	31
7 Conclusions	32
8 References	33
9 Appendix I – SARAS SIMPLIFIED SURGICAL PROCEDURES	34
9.1 <i>SARAS Robotic Assisted Radical Prostatectomy simplified model</i>	34
10 Appendix II – SARAS surgical task-oriented tests	36
10.1 <i>Assistant's tasks of Robotic Assisted Radical Prostatectomy</i>	36
11 Appendix III – SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform evaluation questionnaires	46
12 Appendix IV – SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform questionnaires results	53
12.1 <i>Results of SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform Qualitative Assessment Questionnaire</i>	53
12.2 <i>Results of SARAS Usability Questionnaire</i>	53
12.3 <i>Results of Communication and Coordination questionnaire - first surgeon and assistant</i>	54

List of acronyms

SARAS	Smart Autonomous Robotic Assistant Surgeon
OSR	Ospedale San Raffaele
MM/MS	Multi-Master/Multi-Slave
MIS	Minimally Invasive Surgery
WP	Work Package
OR	Operating Room
AI	Artificial Intelligence
RARP	Robotic Assisted Radical Prostatectomy
LRN	Laparoscopic Radical Nephrectomy
LPN	Laparoscopic Partial Nephrectomy
LR/PN	Laparoscopic Radical/Partial Nephrectomy
QAQ	Qualitative Assessment Questionnaire
GOALS	Global Operative Assessment of Laparoscopic Skills
GEARS	Global Evaluative Assessment of Robotic Skills

List of Tables

Table 1: Participants of the SARAS experiments	16
Table 2: Evaluation of SARAS QAQ – SURG1.....	19
Table 3: Evaluation of SARAS Usability Questionnaire – SURG1	19
Table 4: Evaluation of SARAS Communication and Coordination questionnaire – SURG1.....	20
Table 5: Evaluation of SARAS surgical task-oriented test - SURG3.....	24
Table 6: Evaluation of SARAS QAQ – SURG2 and SURG3.....	25
Table 7: Evaluation of SARAS Usability Questionnaire – SURG2 and SURG3	25
Table 8: Evaluation of SARAS Communication and Coordination questionnaire – SURG2 and SURG3	26
Table 9: Evaluation of SARAS QAQ –SURG4.....	28
Table 10: Evaluation of SARAS Usability Questionnaire –SURG4	29
Table 11: Evaluation of SARAS Communication and Coordination questionnaire – SURG4.....	29

List of Figures

Figure 1: Representation of collapsed bladder.....	13
Figure 2: Phantom with collapsed rectum.....	13
Figure 3: Study of inclination of RARP phantom and the box of phantom, with the trocars inside in the skin.....	14
Figure 4: The vas deferens and seminal vesicles in posterior view: in “real” phantom (left) and in anatomical correct position (right).....	15
Figure 5 First surgeon at the da Vinci console (on left) and SARAS master console (on right).....	16
Figure 6: Peg and Ring test: initial phase (A); ring grasping (B); final phase (C).....	17
Figure 7: Experimental setup of second release of SARAS platform.....	20
Figure 8: Upper traction of bladder.....	26
Figure 9: Anterior prostatic fat dissection with tissue grasping.....	27
Figure 10: Bladder neck transection with catheter holding.....	27
Figure 11: Needles holding for Vesicoureteral anastomosis.....	27
Figure 12: Suture’s t thread cutting at the end of Vesicoureteral anastomosis.....	28

1 Executive summary

The present document “*Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform*” includes:

- The description of the testing activities planned (i.e. the functional tests, as it will be detailed later), in the context of task T1.3, for the validation of the SARAS multi-master/multi-slave (MM/MS) bilateral teleoperation system (i.e. the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform) on the abdominal phantoms developed in WP2;
- The description of the technical and functional pre-tests held, with Ospedale San Raffaele (OSR) surgeons at the Verona’s university laboratory premises, from January to March 2019.
- The description of the results obtained in the functional tests of the SARAS MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform, held with Ospedale San Raffaele (OSR) and Azienda Ospedaliera Universitaria Integrata (AOUI Verona) surgeons in May-June 2019.

2 Introduction

The SARAS research project addresses the topic of automatization in surgical procedures, through the development of general methods for cognitive surgical robots capable of combining sensing, dexterity and cognitive capabilities to carry out autonomously simple surgical actions for two reference procedures: Robotic Assisted Radical Prostatectomy (RARP) and Laparoscopic Radical/Partial Nephrectomy (LR/PN).

2.1 Purpose and structure of the document

The aim of this document is to describe the test plan structured for the SARAS MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform. The activities outlined are meant to be *functional tests*, and not technical ones (which are discussed in Deliverables 3.1 and 7.2), addressing therefore the system as a whole, its ability in carrying out the expected surgical tasks *for the RARP simplified procedure* (see Deliverable 1.1) and its level of usability from the surgeon's point of view. In particular the test plan has been framed in order to:

- Assess the effectiveness of the SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform in performing the expected surgical tasks (outlined in Deliverable 1.1) for the benchmark procedures;
- Investigate the perceived satisfaction in using/operating the SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform from the testers' perspective (i.e. MIS experienced urological surgeons);
- Evaluate the coordination and cooperation of the main surgeon at the da Vinci® IS1200 console and the assistant surgeon tele-operating the SARAS robotic arms;
- Evaluate the impact of force feedback and virtual fixtures on the surgical tasks' performance.

SARAS Deliverable 1.2 is structured as follows:

- The first part (*Chapter 3*) describes the rationale behind the choice of the different functional test and their specific aim;
- *Chapter 4* provides a description of pre-testing phase of the SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform;
- *Chapter 5* describes the results obtained in the functional evaluation of the SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform;
- The attached documents (Annexes to Deliverable 1.2) include the appendices which provide the actual test's details:
 - Appendix I recalls the procedural steps of the SARAS simplified RARP, as it has been described in Deliverable 1.1;
 - Appendix III collects all the other *questionnaires* developed for the present investigation;
 - Appendix IV collects all the aggregated responses to the questionnaires provided by surgeons.

3 SARAS MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform *functional* test plan

The current test plan has been framed into two distinct parts:

- The first one aims at assessing the ability (i.e. the effectiveness) of the developed platform to carry out, in a correct way and on the physical phantom models (implemented in WP2), the different surgical tasks which compose the SARAS simplified RARP described in D1.1.
- The second one aims at evaluating the system performance in a qualitative way, relying on the feedback from expert surgeons who have experienced it.

On the basis of the study of Ereso et al., 2009, which describes and evaluates three prototype tele-operated proctoring platforms, to carry out the functional test plan we aim to collect a participants' pool sample of a maximum of 5 surgeons experienced in robotic-assisted MIS and capable to perform both the first surgeon's and assistant's tasks. A brief pre-test questionnaire has been sketched in order to characterize the participating sample of testers (see Appendix III).

In the following the different test methods are going to be described.

3.1 SARAS surgical task-oriented tests

The modeling of the benchmark RARP performed in T1.1, constitutes the basis on which evaluating the effectiveness of SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform in fulfilling the surgical requirements identified in D1.1 (please see D1.1, chapter 5.2). The system is meant to provide the assistant surgeon a surgical platform which allows him/her to perform all the different tasks, in cooperation with the first surgeon.

To assess this, the involved surgeons will perform the SARAS simplified RARP (as first surgeons or as assistants) on the corresponding physical phantom models (see D1.1, chapter 5.1) with the following surgical systems:

- Da Vinci® standard IS 1200 (see D1.1, chapter 4.1.1), tele-operated by the first surgeon;
- SARAS MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform ((see D3.1 and D7.3), tele-operated by the assistant.

The SARAS simplified procedure is going to be reproduced step by step and audio/video recorded. At the end of the "surgical intervention", each surgeon will complete a surgical-task checklist (see Appendix II), which reports the list of all the assistant's tasks and the corresponding surgical requirements.

3.2 SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform Qualitative Assessment Questionnaire

To further investigate the effectiveness of the SARAS platform, in particular what was the perception of the overall “surgical experience” for the surgeons involved in the tests, we decided to include in the analyses some collateral aspects which could be of interest for the developing the next SARAS autonomous system.

We therefore created a dedicated questionnaire: “*SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform Qualitative Assessment Questionnaire*” (QAQ - see Appendix III), in order to give a qualitative assessment of the SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform, based on the literature reporting similar investigations (Ereso et al., 2009 and Doyle et al., 2007). The SARAS QAQ is divided into two parts: (i) firstly a qualitative performance investigation, centered around the concepts of instrument handling, time, motion, spatial awareness, flow; and (ii) secondly a more quantitative performance assessment focusing on movement accuracy, placement accuracy, and speed. These aspects have to be evaluated on a five-point Operative Performance Rating Scale (OPRS), where a higher score representing better performance (e.g. 5) and a lower score signifying poor performance (e.g. 1). The OPRS was developed based on the previously validated global operative assessment of laparoscopic skills (GOALS) rating scale (Vassiliou et al., 2005). Furthermore, an additional questionnaire, called Global Evaluative Assessment of Robotic Skills (GEARS) has been studied and used as reference to enrich the list of information to include in the SARAS Qualitative Assessment Questionnaire (Aghazadeh, Mercado, Pan, Miles, & Goh, 2016).

The QAQ is meant to be completed by each surgeon covering the role of the assistant, at the end of the task-oriented test.

3.3 SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform Usability Questionnaire

In order to evaluate the SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform, a specific survey has been created to investigate the usability, defined as the level of reached accuracy, efficiency and satisfaction perceived in using a system.

The *Usability survey* (see Appendix III) is based on a classical five-point Likert scale, where a higher score presenting strong agreement (e.g. 5) and a lower score signifying strong disagreement (e.g. 1) and is going to be filled by surgeons playing the role of the assistant, after the QAQ. The survey measures surgeons’ perceptions based on their evaluation of the SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform on the following aspects: movement, control, ease of use, and responsiveness (Ereso et al., 2009).

3.4 *SARAS Communication and Coordination Questionnaires*

Taking inspiration from the work of Marttos et al., 2012, we framed these questionnaires (see Appendix III) to evaluate the communication and coordination between the first and assistant surgeons, during the “surgical performance” mediated by the SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform (Martos et al., 2012).

Both the assistant and the first surgeon will complete this questionnaire at the end of the test session.

4 Description of the SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform pre-tests

The present chapter includes the description of the pre-testing phase of the SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform.

Before undergoing the overall functional test plan, described in Chapter 3, we decided to carry out three pre-test sessions of the MULTIROBOTS platform in the ALTAIR Robotics Lab in Verona, where the Da Vinci® System from Intuitive Surgical Inc. and the SARAS prototype are available. These tests were meant to:

- (i) assess the actual technical status of the SARAS platform - and any possible criticality with it;
- (ii) to pre-run some elementary surgical tasks of the assistant surgeon, involved in the RARP simplified procedure, to be later formally tested;
- (iii) get some feedbacks from surgeons on the phantoms' development.

In order to carry out the simplified RARP procedure, a team of 4 expert urological surgeons of Ospedale San Raffaele (OSR) were involved, each one capable of performing both the main surgeon's and the assistant's roles, so as to take advantage from various points of view and to underline as much as possible the critical factors possibly hampering the procedure's execution.

During the pre-tests execution, however, we encountered some key technical criticalities which, according to the surgeons' feedbacks, prevent a smooth execution of the intended tasks by the SARAS platform. In particular, the most impactful problems encountered were:

- *A limited working space of the SARAS robotic arms:* the robots holding the standard laparoscopic tools (a grasper and a scissor) cannot reach all the needed anatomical structure;
- *A significant delay from the assistant console and SARAS robotic arms* makes the usability of the teleoperation system not easy;
- *The mapping of the orientation of the tools* at the assistant console to the SARAS arms was not as expected by the surgeons;
- *The Phantoms of the abdomen needed some improvements;*
- *The main surgeon cannot control the position of the endoscope.* The dVRK software made available by Intuitive for research institutes to control the da Vinci system does not have right now this feature. According to their wiki there will be a new release of the software by the end of July. In the meantime, this issue cannot be closed, i.e. the endoscope can be only moved manually.

Therefore it was decided, in agreement with the project Coordinator, to focus on the technical resolution of the outlined problems before undergoing any kind of overall evaluation of the system.

Therefore, SARAS partners mainly involved in the hardware and software development carried out the following improvements:

- Re-writing the firmware in C++ instead of Java Script, to solve the issue related to the communication delay from master to slave;

- Re-design of the mechanical structure of the robots holding the standard laparoscopic tools to increase the workspace;
- Validation of the control architecture with the novel hardware to fix some bugs.

In the following, we present the report of the three testing sessions.

4.1 Minutes of first SARAS meeting (22nd January 2019)

As described in Deliverable 2.1 “Patient specific based phantom models”, the last version of RARP phantom was the “Generation 4”, to which had to be added the following characteristics:

- Less and softer tissue left and right of bladder/prostate;
- Reduce stiffness of bladder (and/or collapse bladder);
- Reduce stiffness of “skin” for phantom box (i.e. abdominal wall simulation);
- Option for inclination of entire box (from 0° to. 30°; feet up) as well as of phantom inside of box (from 0° to. 30°; feet down);
- Box should be bigger in size, i.e. giving more room around phantom.

On the 22nd of January, the evaluation of a new set of phantoms has been made by the OSR surgeons involved in the tests (Umberto Capitano, MD and Alessandro Larcher, MD) and some additional modifications for the phantom have been discussed:

- The bladder should be a little bit more collapsed, see Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Representation of collapsed bladder

- The sigmoid colon (or sigma) should be a little bit more collapsed (it is a “virtual” space), see Figure 2 below:

Figure 2: Phantom with collapsed rectum

- The dimension of prostate should be reduced of a 10% respect to a current version and its weight should be more or less of 60 g (by reducing of a 10% you should reach this weight)
- The urethra is a tube and should be empty, without silicone, because the catheter will be inserted in the urethra.
- The phantom's side should be fixed on the plane, in addition to the center of the bone (see Figure 3). The inclination of 30 degrees will be done outside the phantom and there will be another small inclination of the bone (see Figure 3 below) in order to maximise the operating space. The bone will be raised by the box.

In this occasion, it was decided to remove the external box of the phantom, to ease the discussion regarding the position of the da Vinci and SARAS robotic arms.

Figure 3: Study of inclination of RARP phantom and the box of phantom, with the trocars inside in the skin

The main functional and technical criticalities of SARAS MULTIROBOTS encountered during this pre-test were:

- Problem in rescaling the da Vinci movements (decrease the scale ratio) on the master console, the first surgeon has to move “a lot” and clutch the manipulators in order to slightly move the instruments on the end effectors.
- The surgeons reported some criticalities with use of fixed view from the endoscope.
- The SARAS arm had some problem with the mapping of the orientation of the tools handled by the assistant at the SARAS console and the laparoscopic tools mounted at the end-effector of the SARAS slave arms.
- The SARAS teleoperation system had a big communication delay.

4.2 Minutes of second SARAS meeting (15th February 2019)

A new set of phantoms was delivered by the time of the second pre-test, in which they were evaluated by the third OSR surgeon (Nicola Fossati, MD) and additional modifications have to be considered:

- The vas deferens and seminal vesicles should be divided. If possible, the vas deferens (in orange in the figure below) should be moved inside the seminal vesicles (in blue), see Figure 4 on the left side;
- The seminal vesicles are not in direct contact with bladder, but there is a small layer of connective tissue between them (see Figure 4 on the right side).

Figure 4: The vas deferens and seminal vesicles in posterior view: in “real” phantom (left) and in anatomical correct position (right)

The main functional and technical encountered criticalities of SARAS MULTIROBOTS were:

- The working space of the SARAS arms was too small.
- Moreover, some of the previous problems were not solved yet.

4.3 Minutes of third SARAS meeting (27th February 2019)

For this last pre-test was not yet available a new generation of phantoms, however for the upcoming final functional evaluation all the suggested modifications will be included

The main functional and technical criticalities encountered by the attending OSR surgeon (Fabio Muttin, MD) were:

- The working space of the SARAS arms was limited
- The calibration of the SARAS arms should be checked.

5 Functional evaluation of the SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform

The present chapter includes the results of the functional testing phase of the SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform.

The principal aim of the test performed is to assess the effectiveness of MM/MS bilateral teleoperation system and focus on its usability aspects, on the basis of direct feedback from surgeons' experiences while using SARAS (Figure 5).

Figure 5 First surgeon at the da Vinci console (on left) and SARAS master console (on right)

The experiments have been held in the ALTAIR Robotics Lab in Verona, where the Da Vinci® System from Intuitive Surgical Inc. and the SARAS prototype are available. We performed three test sessions in three different days (17th May 2019; 31st May 2019; 19th June 2019).

A sample of 4 urological surgeons, capable of performing R-MIS (even if with different level of experience: 2 are experienced surgeons, 2 are residents) has been involved in the tests.

Table 1 reports an overview of the sample characterization:

Code	Qualification	Num. of laparoscopic surgeries as first surgeon	Num. of laparoscopic surgeries as assistant	Num. of R-MIS as first surgeon	Num. of R-MIS as assistant
SURG1	Surgeon	1-50	50-100	1-50	>100
SURG2	Resident	1-50	1-50	1-50	>100
SURG3	Resident	1-50	1-50	1-50	1-50
SURG4	Surgeon	1-50	1-50	50-100	>100

Table 1: Participants of the SARAS experiments

The functional tests were structured as follows:

1) An initial training phase

In order to familiarize with the MM/MS teleoperation system, all the surgeons had the possibility to use SARAS up to 30 minutes and exercising in simple tasks deriving from the laparoscopic training modules, e.g. the peg and ring exercise or grasping and passing a ring between the SARAS end effectors (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Peg and Ring test: initial phase (A); ring grasping (B); final phase (C)

2) A simulation of RARP simplified procedure

The RARP simplified procedure (see Deliverable 1.1, Paragraph 4.1.4) have been reproduced step by step and audio/video recorded.

We carried out the three test session of RARP simplified procedure, taking care to standardize as much as possible the communication between the first and second surgeon. This has been done in order to put the basis for the future development of an appropriate glossary for the autonomous SARAS platform, which is supposed to interact with the first surgeon also through verbal commands.

3) Assessment of the effectiveness and usability of the SARAS platform with different surveys (described in Chapter 3).

At the end of the execution of the simplified RARP, each surgeon completed a surgical-task checklist and the Quality Assessment Questionnaire, Usability Survey and Communication and Coordination Questionnaire (see Appendix II).

It is worth noting that, for the current test plan, three different SARAS platform releases were used due to a different level of affordability of the sw and hw components. Here below is reported a short description of the technical problems encountered in each release and how they were fixed in the next one. The results of the tests are going to be interpreted and discussed on the basis of these specific problems.

1°release of SARAS platform (17th May 2019):

The measurements of the tool tip positions and the remote center of motion were not accurate during normal robot operation. Furthermore, during the contact with the environment, or when the target pose was not reachable (outside the robot workspace), there were wrong measurements of the current pose. This makes the teleoperation unusable and forced us to switch the system off and on.

2°release of SARAS platform (31st May 2019):

Problems with the measurements and the tool tip position have been solved. The system was still unrecoverable when the target pose was unreachable. We were able to identify the problem: The robot motor failure caused the remote center of motion to move whereas it should stay fixed. To use again the teleoperation system, the EGS should be manually moved to bring the remote center of motion back to the original place.

3°release of SARAS platform (19th June 2019)

The software problems related to measurements and movement functions have been solved. The last version of the robot firmware allows to set a target position with the constraint of a fixed remote center of motion guaranteed via software. The software constraint is more precise than the hardware constraint provided by the assistant master console. The teleoperation architecture has been improved as well, by modifying the ergonomics of the master console for the assistant: the "joysticks" are now mechanically aligned with the laparoscopic tools on the SARAS arms making the remote controlling easier. Furthermore, the measurement precision of the poses and the velocity of the robot were both increased. The teleoperation is now much more intuitive.

A mechanical failure prevents to grasp objects in particular conditions. The EGS is in this moment under repairing.

5.1 Results of the first evaluation - 17th May 2019

The first part of the test, the execution of the simplified RARP procedure, was carried out with SURG1 performing the first surgeon role at the da Vinci console and a SARAS experienced technician working on the MMMS tele-operated system and covering the role of the assistant. They were able to complete the simplified procedure.

When the roles were shifted, and SURG1 was supposed to tele-operate with SARAS as the assistant, unfortunately a technical problem occurred, blocking the right SARAS arm and preventing the completion of the procedure. Therefore, SURG1 could not fill in the assistant’s check list.

Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4 report respectively the evaluations of the Quality Assessment, Usability and Communication/Coordination questionnaires. It has to be noted that SURG 1 couldn’t answer to second Communication and Coordination questionnaire (the one related to the assistant surgeon), due to the problems related to the blocking of the SARAS right robotic arm, preventing the execution of the second procedure.

Handling of instruments	Spatial awareness	Time and motion	Depth perception	Bimanual dexterity	Efficiency	Force sensitivity	Movement accuracy	Placement accuracy	Speed
4	4	3	3	4	4	3	3	3	3

Table 2: Evaluation of SARAS QAQ – SURG1

	SURG1
1. The quality of the overall experience was good	4
2. The surgical movements were translated accurately by the robotic platform	3
3. The robotic surgical arms moved responsively	3
4. The robotic platform was adequate in completing the tasks	3
5. The status of the robotic platform is always clear	3
6. The visual equipment is helpful and appropriate	4
7. The actions of the robotic platform match actions performed by the user (i.e.: time delay,direction of motion, depth perception...)	3
8. The robotic platform allows to recover from errors consistently	3
9. The operator of the robotic platform is always in control of any tasks or actions in the process	2
10. The robotic platform does not contain unnecessary or misleading information	3
11. There is enough guidance/support to reduce the effort for the users	3
12. The situation (actions, messages, feedbacks) presented by the robotic platform are clear and self-explanatory	2
13. All the provided guidance/support information is useful and easy to understand	3
14. The information provided by the robotic platform is easy to understand	3

Table 3: Evaluation of SARAS Usability Questionnaire – SURG1

	Main Surgeon
Communication skills	3
1. I was able communicate effectively	3
2. I felt staff/remote physician able to understand my questions and comments	3
3. I felt comfortable communicating with staff from my telesurgery location	3
4. I was able to hear clinical information and exchanges clearly	3

Table 4: Evaluation of SARAS Communication and Coordination questionnaire – SURG1

5.2 Results of the second evaluation - 31st May 2019

The second SARAS functional test session was held on 31st May 2019 with two surgeons: SURG2 and 3, which alternated in covering the first and assistant roles. They used the second release of the SARAS platform which had serious technical criticalities, therefore hampering the execution of the entire simplified RARP procedure (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Experimental setup of second release of SARAS platform

The phases that were possible to reproduce were: (3) bladder mobilization; (4) anterior prostatic fat dissection; (5) bladder neck transection.

The assistant completed a “SARAS surgical task-oriented test”, which reports the list of all the assistant’s tasks and the corresponding surgical requirements. The assistant’s evaluations, with the requirements fulfilled during tasks’ execution and their feedback/notes/comments are in Table 5.

D1.2 Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform

Phase Code	Phase	Step	Assistant Task	Surgical Action	Of What?	Instrument type	Requirements for surgical actions (sub-task)		Task fulfillment (yes/no)	Notes
1	Incision of the peritoneum and entry into the retropubic space of Retzius	2	Upper anterior traction on the peritoneum	Holding (Traction)	Peritoneum	Grasper	R.1.2.A.1	Identify the Peritoneum		Not performed
							R.1.2.A.2	Identify the region of the Peritoneum to be grasped		Not performed
							R.1.2.A.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region		Not performed
							R.1.2.A.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		Not performed
							R.1.2.A.5	Grasp the target region		Not performed
							R.1.2.A.6	Plan the direction of the requested upper-anterior traction		Not performed
							R.1.2.A.7	Implement and maintain the traction		Not performed
			Upper anterior traction / Suction and cleaning of blood	Traction / Suction	Peritoneum / Blood	Suction-irrigator	R.1.2.B.1	Identify the Peritoneum		Not performed
							R.1.2.B.2	Identify the region of the Peritoneum to be pushed		Not performed
							R.1.2.B.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region		Not performed
							R.1.2.B.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		Not performed
							R.1.2.B.5	Plan the direction for the upper traction		Not performed
							R.1.2.B.6	Implement and maintain the traction		Not performed
							3	Bladder mobilization	1	Upper traction of the bladder/ Suction and cleaning of blood
R.3.1.2	Identify the region of the Bladder to be moved	YES								

D1.2 Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform

						R.3.1.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region	YES		
						R.3.1.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments	NO	<i>A lot of collisions/conflicts with da Vinci instruments</i>	
						R.3.1.5	Plan the direction for the upper traction	YES		
						R.3.1.6	Implement and maintain the traction	NO	<i>Grasper instrument doesn't close properly</i>	
4	Anterior prostatic fat (AFP) dissection	1	Upper traction of the prostatic fat/ Suction and cleaning of blood	Traction / Suction	Prostatic fat/ Blood	Suction-irrigator	R.4.1.1	Identify the Prostatic Fat	YES	
							R.4.1.2	Identify the region of the Prostatic Fat to be moved	YES	
							R.4.1.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region	YES	
							R.4.1.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments	NO	<i>Not reached the task, because of collisions of instruments</i>
							R.4.1.5	Plan the direction for the upper traction	YES	
							R.4.1.6	Implement and maintain the traction	YES	
		2	The assistant provides the prostatic fat's traction	Holding (Traction)	Prostatic fat	Grasper	R.4.2.1	Identify the Prostatic Fat	YES	
							R.4.2.2	Identify the region of the Prostatic Fat to be grasped	YES	
							R.4.2.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region	YES	
							R.4.2.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments	NO	<i>A lot of collisions/conflicts with da Vinci instruments</i>
						R.4.2.5	Grasp the target region	YES		

D1.2 Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform

						R.4.2.6	Plan the direction of the requested traction	YES		
						R.4.2.7	Implement and maintain the traction	NO	<i>Improve the strength of grasper</i>	
6	Bladder neck transection	1	Upper traction/ Suction and cleaning blood	Traction / Suction	Bladder / Blood	Suction-irrigator	R.6.1.1	Identify the Bladder	YES	
							R.6.1.2	Identify the region of the Bladder to be moved	YES	
							R.6.1.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region	YES	
							R.6.1.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments	NO	<i>A lot of collisions/conflicts with da Vinci instruments</i>
							R.6.1.5	Plan the direction for the upper traction	YES	
							R.6.1.6	Implement and maintain the traction	NO	
		3	Move the catheter from a surgeon's grasper to assistant's grasper	Holding (Catheter)	Catheter	Grasper	R.6.3.1	Identify the Catheter and the da Vinci grasper holding it	YES	<i>Improve the strength of grasper</i>
							R.6.3.2	Identify the region of the Catheter to be grasped	YES	
							R.6.3.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region	YES	
							R.6.3.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments	NO	<i>A lot of collisions/conflicts with da Vinci instruments</i>
							R.6.3.5	Grasp the chosen Catheter region	YES	
R.6.3.6	Maintain it in position						YES			

D1.2 Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform

							R.6.4.1	Identify the Catheter and the SV	YES	
							R.6.4.2	Identify the region of the Catheter and the SV to be grasped together	YES	
							R.6.4.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target regions	YES	
		4	Catheter and seminal vesicles are handed to the assistant for upper traction	Holding (Traction)	Catheter Seminal vesicles (SV)	Grasper	R.6.4.4	Reach the target regions without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments	YES	
							R.6.4.5	Grasp the target regions	YES	
							R.6.4.6	Plan the direction of the requested upper-traction	YES	
							R.6.4.7	Implement and maintain the traction	NO	<i>END OF EXPERIMENT because of technical problem occurred</i>

Table 5: Evaluation of SARAS surgical task-oriented test - SURG3

Table 6, Table 7 and Table 8 report respectively the evaluations of the Quality Assessment, Usability and Communication/Coordination questionnaires from the two surgeons.

Code	Handling of instruments	Spatial awareness	Time and motion	Depth perception	Bimanual dexterity	Efficiency	Force sensitivity	Movement accuracy	Placement accuracy	Speed
SURG2	3	2	3	2	3	2	2	2	3	2
SURG3	2	2	1	2	3	1	2	2	2	2

Table 6: Evaluation of SARAS QAQ – SURG2 and SURG3

	SURG2	SURG3
1. The quality of the overall experience was good	3	3
2. The surgical movements were translated accurately by the robotic platform	2	2
3. The robotic surgical arms moved responsively	2	2
4. The robotic platform was adequate in completing the tasks	2	1
5. The status of the robotic platform is always clear	1	2
6. The visual equipment is helpful and appropriate	1	3
7. The actions of the robotic platform match actions performed by the user (i.e.: time delay, direction of motion, depth perception...)	2	3
8. The robotic platform allows to recover from errors consistently	2	2
9. The operator of the robotic platform is always in control of any tasks or actions in the process	1	2
10. The robotic platform does not contain unnecessary or misleading information	2	2
11. There is enough guidance/support to reduce the effort for the users	1	2
12. The situation (actions, messages, feedbacks) presented by the robotic platform are clear and self explanatory	1	3
13. All the provided guidance/support information is useful and easy to understand	2	2
14. The information provided by the robotic platform is easy to understand	2	2

Table 7: Evaluation of SARAS Usability Questionnaire – SURG2 and SURG3

	SURG2		SURG3	
	Main Surgeon	Assistant	Main Surgeon	Assistant
Communication skills	4	4	0	2
1. I was able communicate effectively	5	5	0	2
2. I felt staff/remote physician able to understand my questions and comments	5	5	0	2
3. I felt comfortable communicating with staff from my telesurgery location	5	5	0	2
4. I was able to hear clinical information and exchanges clearly	5	5	0	2

Table 8: Evaluation of SARAS Communication and Coordination questionnaire – SURG2 and SURG3

5.3 Results of the third evaluation - 19th June 2019

The last SARAS session test was held on 19th June 2019 with SURG4, performing the first surgeon role at the da Vinci console, and an SARAS experienced technician worked as assistant on the MMMS tele-operated system. They were able to complete the RARP simplified procedure, without interruptions. In the following, a list of assistant’s action performed by assistant during RARP simulation is identified, including the experimental figures:

- Upper traction of the bladder with SARAS arms (RARP simplified procedure - phase 3). The assistant helped the first surgeon to collapse the bladder, in order to increase the working space of surgery (Figure 8);

Figure 8: Upper traction of bladder

- Tissue grasping with grasper instrument in SARAS left arm (RARP simplified procedure - phase 4). The assistant moved out the prostatic fat (Figure 9);

Figure 9: Anterior prostatic fat dissection with tissue grasping

- Catheter holding with grasper instrument in SARAS left arm (RARP simplified procedure - phase 6). The assistant moved out the prostatic fat (Figure 10);

Figure 10: Bladder neck transection with catheter holding

- Niddles grasping with grasper instrument in SARAS left arm (RARP simplified procedure - phase 13). The assistant passed the needle and the suture thread to the surgeon for Vesicoureteral anastomosis (Figure 11);

Figure 11: Needles holding for Vesicoureteral anastomosis

- Suture’s thread cutting with scissor instrument in SARAS right arm (RARP simplified procedure - phase 13) (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Suture’s t thread cutting at the end of Vesicoureteral anastomosis

Then the roles were switched. In this case it has to be noted that, the being the technician not a surgeon, it was difficult for him to reproduce the RARP tasks as a first surgeon operating at da Vinci console. Despite this, SURG4 was able to test the SARAS robotics arms with some elementary tasks (e.g. peg and ring; suture’s thread cutting; needle grasping; specific trajectory following with grasper instrument). For this reason it was not possible for SURG4 to answer the assistant’s part of the Communication and Coordination questionnaire.

Table 9, Table 10, Table 11 show respectively the evaluations of the Quality Assessment, Usability and Communication/Coordination questionnaires.

Handling of instruments	Spatial awareness	Time and motion	Depth perception	Bimanual dexterity	Efficiency	Force sensitivity	Movement accuracy	Placement accuracy	Speed
4	4	4	2	3	3	2	4	4	3

Table 9: Evaluation of SARAS QAQ –SURG4

	SURG4
1. The quality of the overall experience was good	4
2. The surgical movements were translated accurately by the robotic platform	3
3. The robotic surgical arms moved responsively	4
4. The robotic platform was adequate in completing the tasks	3
5. The status of the robotic platform is always clear	4
6. The visual equipment is helpful and appropriate	2
7. The actions of the robotic platform match actions performed by the user (i.e.: time delay,direction of motion, depth perception...)	2
8. The robotic platform allows to recover from errors consistently	2

D1.2 Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform

9. The operator of the robotic platform is always in control of any tasks or actions in the process	3
10. The robotic platform does not contain unnecessary or misleading information	3
11. There is enough guidance/support to reduce the effort for the users	2
12. The situation (actions, messages, feedbacks) presented by the robotic platform are clear and self explanatory	4
13. All the provided guidance/support information is useful and easy to understand	3
14. The information provided by the robotic platform is easy to understand	4

Table 10: Evaluation of SARAS Usability Questionnaire –SURG4

	Main Surgeon
Communication skills	4
1. I was able communicate effectively	3
2. I felt staff/remote physician able to understand my questions and comments	4
3. I felt comfortable communicating with staff from my telesurgery location	4
4. I was able to hear clinical information and exchanges clearly	4

Table 11: Evaluation of SARAS Communication and Coordination questionnaire – SURG4

6 Discussion on the results obtained

6.1 Qualitative Assessment Questionnaire

As it is clear from Table 2, the overall qualitative assessment of SARAS from SURG1 is quite positive, despite the presence of some hardware problems that led to the interruption of the test, when he was performing the role of the assistant. This could be explained by the fact that SURG1 is the reference OSR surgeon for the SARAS project, so probably his fairly positive evaluation might be influenced by the fact that he rewarded the incremental SARAS improvements.

Looking, instead at the evaluation of SURG2 and 3 (Table 6), it can be seen that the two surgeons expressed more or less the same assessment, with a low score (from 3 downwards) assigned to the overall experience. In particular, from the evaluations provided by SURG2, it is clear that some difficulties have emerged in: *(i)* the awareness of the space occupied by the SARAS robotic arms – a non-intuitively understandable work space; *(ii)* the spatial depth perception, due to the lack of virtual fixtures (i.e. of sensory information increased on the perception by the surgeon of a virtual environment); *(iii)* the precision of the instruments' movements; *(iv)* the efficiency (i.e. the progression of the action is not fluid, but is discontinuous) and *(v)* the speed movement of the robotic arms (slowness of the movement). The same difficulties are reflected in the responses of SURG3 where, in addition, he also experienced problems in reaching the target, due to many unnecessary movements, with a consequent increase in the duration of the surgical task.

The last qualitative evaluation from SURG4 (Table 9) is overall positive, because there was an important technical improvement in this third release of SARAS platform, relative to: *(i)* the speed of SARAS arms; *(ii)* the precision of the movement; *(iii)* the positioning of the robotic arms, *(iv)* the efficiency and *(v)* the awareness in space, that resulted in the most positive completion of the simplified RARP. It is worth noting that the depth perception remains the only experienced problem to be solved.

6.2 Usability Survey

The overall usability evaluation of SURG1 (Table 3) is neutral, and this is in line with the brief experience he had with the SARAS platform. It is interesting noting that the negative evaluations are related to the fact that the robotic arms often were driven outside their working space (answer num. 9), which reflects the same impression of SURG2 and 3, and that SARAS system messages/feedbacks were not always clear (answer num. 12).

Both SURG2 and 3 provided a negative usability evaluation (Table 7), reporting problems related to: *(i)* the reactivity of the robotic arms, *(ii)* the inadequacy of the robotic platform in completing a surgical task, *(iii)* the lack of clarity in the state of the robotic platform (missing clear feedbacks), *(iv)*

the inadequacy of the images inside the Oculus Rift, that remain fixed even if the surgeon moves his head, causing a feeling of nausea. This last aspect has been reported also by SURG 4, but the global evaluation is the best one collected. This is this is attributable to the technical improvements of the latest release of the platform, related to: *(i)* the increase in the speed of SARAS robotic arms movements, *(ii)* the greater reactivity of the robotic arms and *(iii)* a greater understanding of the information provided by the robotic platform.

6.3 *Communication and Coordination Questionnaires*

SURG1 and SURG4 provided a neutral and quite positive assessment, respectively, to this aspect of the evaluation, and only related to the “first surgeon role”, because they didn’t had the chance to tele-operate with SARAS arms as assistants in the RARP simplified procedure.

SURG2 scored a high evaluation of the communication skills, both for the role of the main surgeon and the assistant one; while SURG 3 was able only to rate the communication as assistant, because of the impossibility to complete the second round of the RARP simplified procedure (where he was supposed to be the first surgeon) due to technical problems. The different, and low, rating of SURG3 could be interpreted as a result of SURG2 effort to use a standardized lexicon to communicate during the operation, which at times was not very intuitive.

7 Conclusions

The results of the surveys are consistent with the different releases of the SARAS platform.

The rating values ranged from score values of 5 (agree strongly) to 1 (disagree strongly). The higher the values, the more positive the expression of usability according to the sample of respondents. In general, mean score values from 3.5 and above are adequate expression of usability.

The score 3 is the mid-point value of the rating and this index expresses the neutral opinion. The comments of surgeons are collected referring to the usability problem they have experimented during the use of the system. The results obtained from the analysis of usability will be used as feedback for SARAS product improvement.

At the end of experimental tests, all surgeons highlighted the difficulty in using for the first time the SARAS platform, because it is different from the da Vinci console or any laparoscopic application. All surgeons needed a training session with simple exercises (for example: peg and ring or grasping of a ring), before being confident in starting the RARP procedure. Although all surgeons tried up to 30 minutes of exercise, they have stressed the need to become even more familiar with the system, because it is not yet so intuitive to be used.

In the following, we have some considerations about the results of questionnaires, which are shown in an aggregated overview in Appendix IV:

- A limited working space was a problem in all test sessions, even if it was slightly improved in the last test with third release of SARAS platform, when many hardware problems were solved;
- All questions relating to force feedback are assessed as neutral or bad. The introduction of force feedback could help the operation to be realistic;
- A delay from the assistant console and SARAS robotic arms is reduced respect the pre-testing phase;
- The speed of SARAS arms is quite good;
- The state of the system is unclear, because the virtual fixtures are not implemented. The presence of additional information could help the doctors to understand what is happening;
- The communication and coordination between two surgeons is important, but it was complicated when the glossary was introduced. The surgeon will have to do training on the glossary to use, because it is not so intuitive.

8 References

- Aghazadeh, M. A., Mercado, M. A., Pan, M. M., Miles, B. J., & Goh, A. C. (2016). Performance of robotic simulated skills tasks is positively associated with clinical robotic surgical performance. *BJU International*, *118*(3), 475–481. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bju.13511>
- Doyle, J. D., Webber, E. M., & Sidhu, R. S. (2007). A universal global rating scale for the evaluation of technical skills in the operating room. *American Journal of Surgery*, *193*(5 SPEC. ISS.), 551–555. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjsurg.2007.02.003>
- Ereso, A. Q., Garcia, P., Tseng E., Dua M. M., Victorino, G. P., & Guy T. S. (2009). Usability of Robotic Platforms for Remote Surgical Teleproctoring. *TELEMEDICINE and e-HEALTH*, *15*(5), 445–453
- Marttos, A., Kuchkarian, F. M., Palaios, E., Rojas, D., Abreu-Reis, P., & Schulman, C. (2012). Surgical telepresence: The usability of a robotic communication platform. *World Journal of Emergency Surgery*, *7*(Suppl 1), S11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1749-7922-7-S1-S11>
- Vassiliou, M. C., Feldman, L. S., Andrew, C. G., Bergman, S., Leffondré, K., Stanbridge, D., & Fried, G. M. (2005). A global assessment tool for evaluation of intraoperative laparoscopic skills. *American Journal of Surgery*, *190*(1), 107–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjsurg.2005.04.004>

9 Appendix I – SARAS SIMPLIFIED SURGICAL PROCEDURES

9.1 SARAS Robotic Assisted Radical Prostatectomy simplified model

Phase code	Phase	Step	Anatomical site	Forbidden Region	Main Surgeon task	Surgical Action	Instrument type	Trocar	Assistant Task	Surgical Action	Of What?	Instrument type	Trocar
Initial Phase	Patient positioning		NA	NA	The patient is positioned in the supine position. In da Vinci SARAS Standard: the legs are separated in semi flexion (lithotomy position). Trendelenburg position is 30° from horizontal and a 18 ch Foley catheter is inserted into the bladder						NA	NA	
	Pneumoperitoneum		Peritoneum		A Veress needle (or Hasson trocar) is inserted at the periumbilical position (at 12 mmHg)							Hasson trocar	1
	Port placement		Peritoneum		There are three robotic arms and two assistant ports. The Veress needle is replaced by a 12 mm port and the laparoscope is introduced for initial abdomen inspection. Two 8mm ports are placed for the robotic arm (separate at the right and left side of the camera port). One 5mm assistance port is placed at the right lateral to the camera port and the other 15mm assistance port above the right anterior superior iliac crest.								
1	Incision of the peritoneum and entry into the retropubic space of Retzius	1	Peritoneum		Direct visualization of the peritoneum overlying the bladder		Laparoscope	1					
		2	Retropubic space of Retzius	Bladder pelvic wall	A peritoneal incision is made through the median umbilical ligament to enter in the retropubic space	Traction	Bipolar grasper	3	Upper anterior traction on the peritoneum	Holding (Traction)	Retropubic space of Retzius	Grasper	5
						Incision	Scissor	2	Upper anterior traction / Suction and cleaning of blood	Traction / Suction	Peritoneum / Blood	Suction/irrigator	4
2	Incision of the endopelvic fascia (EPF) and identification of the dorsal venous complex (DVC)	1	Endopelvic fascia	Pelvic wall	Incision of the endopelvic fascia (EPF)	Incision	Scissor	2	Suction and cleaning of smoke and blood	Suction	Blood	Suction/irrigator	4
									The assistant provides the bladder's counter-traction	Holding (Traction)	Bladder	Grasper	5
3	Bladder mobilization	1	Bladder		The bladder is then liberated off the anterior surface of the abdominal wall	Movement	Bipolar grasper	3	Upper traction of the bladder/ Suction and cleaning of blood	Traction / Suction	Bladder / Blood	Suction/irrigator	4
4	Anterior prostatic fat (AFP) dissection	1	Anterior surface of the prostate		The layer of fat is removed to allow better visualization of the puboprostic ligaments, the dorsal venous complex as well as the junction between the bladder neck and the prostate	Dissection	Scissor	2	Upper traction of the prostatic fat/ Suction and cleaning of blood	Traction / Suction	Prostatic fat/ Blood	Suction/irrigator	4
									The assistant provides the prostatic fat's traction	Holding (Traction)	Prostatic fat	Grasper	5
			2							The assistant passes the needle and the suture thread to the surgeon	Holding (Traction)		Locking grasper
5	DVC control and suture	1	DVC	Pubic bone	A total of two suture ligations are put in place (one distal and another more proximal).	Surgical sutures	Needle Driver	2+3	The assistant cuts the suture's thread	Cutting	Suture's thread	Scissor	5
									The needles are snapped out and removed from the body	Holding (Needle)	Needle	Grasper	4
6	Bladder neck incision	1	Bladder Neck	Bladder and prostate	The bladder neck is divided horizontally until the urethral catheter is identified	Transection	Scissor	2	Upper traction/ Suction and cleaning blood	Traction / Suction	Bladder / Blood	Suction/irrigator	4
		2	Urethra		The Foley catheter balloon is then deflated by the nurse								
		3	Urethra		Move the catheter from a surgeon's grasper to assistant's grasper		Bipolar grasper	3	Move the catheter from a surgeon's grasper to assistant's grasper	Holding	Catheter Seminal vesicles	Grasper	5
		4	Prostate		Catheter and seminal vesicles are collectively grasped, pulled through the open bladder neck		Bipolar grasper	3	Catheter and seminal vesicles are handed to the assistant for upper traction	Holding (Traction)	Catheter	Grasper	5
		5	Prostate		The prostate is suspended anteriorly towards the abdominal wall by grasping the internal tip of the catheter and lifting it upwards	Traction	Bipolar grasper	3	Hemoclips are applied to avoid branches of the dorsal vein fanning over the prostate and to prevent unwanted bleeding	Putting Hemoclip/s	Fibrovascular tissue	Automatic Clip Applier	4
7	Vas deferens and arteries are exposed	1	Vas deferens Seminal vesicles	Ureter and bladder	Dissection of the retroprostatic tissue, the vas deferens and accompanying arteries are exposed	Traction	Bipolar grasper	3	Upper anterior traction on the peritoneum	Holding (Traction)	Retroprostatic tissue	Grasper	4
						Dissection	Scissor	2	Suction and cleaning of smoke and blood	Suction	Smoke	Suction/irrigator	5
8	Division of vas deferens	1	Surroundings of seminal vesicles	Ureter and bladder	Uses the grasper as a spatula to free adjoining vessels	Movement	Bipolar grasper	3	The vas deferens are controlled using the Hemoclips	Putting Hemoclip/s	Vas deferens	Automatic Clip Applier	4
		2			Incision of vas deferens	Incision	Scissor	2	Suction and cleaning of smoke and blood	Suction	Smoke	Suction/irrigator	5

D1.2 Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform

Phase code	Phase	Step	Anatomical site	Forbidden Region	Main Surgeon task	Surgical Action	Instrument type	Trocar	Assistant Task	Surgical Action	Of What?	Instrument type	Trocar	
9	Exposure of the seminal vesicles	1	fibrovascular tissue	Ureter and bladder	Blunt dissection of fibrovascular tissue is overlying the surface of the seminal vesicles	Dissection	Scissor	2	The fibrovascular tissue is controlled using the clips	Putting Hemoclip/s	Fibrovascular tissue	Automatic Clip Applier	4	
		2	Seminal vesicles	Ureter and bladder	The surgeon indicates to the assistant where s/he can put the clips				Upper traction of the seminal vesicles	Holding (Traction)	Seminal vesicles	Grasper	5	
									The seminal vesicles are controlled using the clips	Putting Hemoclip/s	Seminal vesicles	Automatic Clip Applier	4	
		3	Seminal vesicles	Ureter and bladder					The seminal vesicle is grasped to help liberate the posterior avascular plane.	Holding (Traction)	Seminal vesicle	Grasper	5	
4	Denonvillier's fascia	Rectum		Deep posterior dissection is then continued to the level of Denonvillier's fascia (or rectovesical space)	Dissection	Scissor	2	Suction and cleaning of smoke and blood	Suction	Blood	Suction-irrigator	5		
10	Neurovascular bundle (NVB) dissection (nerve sparing)	1	Neurovascular bundle		Uses an athermal dissection technique in the proximity of the nerve bundles	Dissection	Monopolar cauterization	2	Allows for proximal control placing Hemoclips	Putting Hemoclip/s	Fibrovascular tissue	Automatic Clip Applier	4	
		2	Neurovascular bundle		Sharp scissor cutting between the nerves to help liberate the tissue	Cut	Sharp scissor	2	Traction/ Suction and cleaning blood	Traction / Suction	Fibrovascular tissue	Suction/irrigator	4	
11	Urethral division	1	Urethra		Sharp scissor cutting through the anterior urethral wall allows for visualization of the Foley catheter	Cut	Scissor	2	Traction/ Suction and cleaning blood	Traction / Suction	Urethra / Blood	Suction/irrigator	4	
		2	Prostate		The remaining posterior wall, including the rectourethralis fibers, is then cut sharply to liberate the prostate	Dissection	Scissor	2	Seminal vesicles are collectively grasped	Holding (Traction)	Seminal vesicle	Grasper	5	
Suction and cleaning of smoke and blood	Suction								Blood	Suction/irrigator	4			
12	Prostate delocation		Prostate		Move the prostate from a surgeon's grasper to assistant's grasper		Bipolar grasper	3	Move the prostate from a surgeon's grasper to assistant's grasper	Holding	Endocatch bag with prostate	Endocatch bag	5	
									The prostate is placed in an endocatch bag along with the anterior prostatic fat and is placed in the upper abdominal space for later retrieval	Holding	Endocatch bag with prostate	Endocatch bag	5	
13	Vesicourethral anastomosis	1	Urethra/ Bladder	Pelvic wall	The well-dissected bladder is free and mobile and can be easily descended into the pelvis.	Surgical sutures	Bipolar grasper	3	The assistant passes the needle and the suture thread to the surgeon	Holding (Needles)	Needles	Grasper	5	
		2		Pelvic wall	The nurse fills up the bladder with water to check the correct operation									
		3								The assistant cuts the suture's thread	Cutting	Suture's thread	Scissor	4
										The needles are snapped out and removed from the body	Holding (Needles)	Needles	Grasper	5
		4	Urethra/ Bladder	Pelvic wall		The hemostatic materials are inserted in the body					Holding	Hemostatic materials	Grasper	4
5		Pelvic wall		The string for the laparoscopic entrapment sack is transferred to the camera port site at the umbilicus and the abdomen is completely deflated					Holding	Endocatch bag	Endocatch bag	5		
14	Endocatch bag Extraction								The specimens within the laparoscopic entrapment sack are extracted intact through extension of the periumbilical trocar site (usually 2.5 cm to 3.5 cm in length)				1	
End	Ports closure								The fascial defect is then immediately closed by sutures. The skin defects are then closed with a subcuticular absorbable suture followed by the skin adhesive Dermabond					

10 Appendix II – SARAS surgical task-oriented tests

10.1 Assistant’s tasks of Robotic Assisted Radical Prostatectomy

Phase Code	Phase	Step	Assistant Task	Surgical Action	Of What?	Instrument type	Requirements for surgical actions (sub-task)		Task fulfillment (yes/no)	Notes
1	Incision of the peritoneum and entry into the retropubic space of Retzius	2	Upper anterior traction on the peritoneum	Holding (Traction)	Peritoneum	Grasper	R.1.2.A.1	Identify the Peritoneum		
							R.1.2.A.2	Identify the region of the Peritoneum to be grasped		
							R.1.2.A.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region		
							R.1.2.A.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		
							R.1.2.A.5	Grasp the target region		
							R.1.2.A.6	Plan the direction of the requested upper-anterior traction		
							R.1.2.A.7	Implement and maintain the traction		
			Upper anterior traction / Suction and cleaning of blood	Traction / Suction	Peritoneum / Blood	Suction-irrigator	R.1.2.B.1	Identify the Peritoneum		
							R.1.2.B.2	Identify the region of the Peritoneum to be pushed		
							R.1.2.B.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region		
							R.1.2.B.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		
							R.1.2.B.5	Plan the direction for the upper traction		

D1.2 Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform

							R.1.2.B.6	Implement and maintain the traction		
3	Bladder mobilization	1	Upper traction of the bladder/ Suction and cleaning of blood	Traction / Suction	Bladder / Blood	Suction-irrigator	R.3.1.1	Identify the Bladder		
							R.3.1.2	Identify the region of the Bladder to be moved		
							R.3.1.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region		
							R.3.1.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		
							R.3.1.5	Plan the direction for the upper traction		
							R.3.1.6	Implement and maintain the traction		
4	Anterior prostatic fat (AFP) dissection	1	Upper traction of the prostatic fat/ Suction and cleaning of blood	Traction / Suction	Prostatic fat/ Blood	Suction-irrigator	R.4.1.1	Identify the Prostatic Fat		
							R.4.1.2	Identify the region of the Prostatic Fat to be moved		
							R.4.1.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region		
							R.4.1.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		
							R.4.1.5	Plan the direction for the upper traction		
							R.4.1.6	Implement and maintain the traction		
		2	The assistant provides the prostatic fat's traction	Holding (Traction)	Prostatic fat	Grasper	R.4.2.1	Identify the Prostatic Fat		
							R.4.2.2	Identify the region of the Prostatic Fat to be grasped		
							R.4.2.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region		

D1.2 Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform

							R.4.2.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		
							R.4.2.5	Grasp the target region		
							R.4.2.6	Plan the direction of the requested traction		
							R.4.2.7	Implement and maintain the traction		
6	Bladder neck transection	1	Upper traction/ Suction and cleaning blood	Traction / Suction	Bladder / Blood	Suction-irrigator	R.6.1.1	Identify the Bladder		
							R.6.1.2	Identify the region of the Bladder to be moved		
							R.6.1.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region		
							R.6.1.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		
							R.6.1.5	Plan the direction for the upper traction		
							R.6.1.6	Implement and maintain the traction		
		3	Move the catheter from a surgeon's grasper to assistant's grasper	Holding (Catheter)	Catheter	Grasper	R.6.3.1	Identify the Catheter and the da Vinci grasper holding it		
							R.6.3.2	Identify the region of the Catheter to be grasped		
							R.6.3.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region		
							R.6.3.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		

D1.2 Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform

						R.6.3.5	Grasp the chosen Catheter region			
						R.6.3.6	Maintain it in position			
		4	Catheter and seminal vesicles are handed to the assistant for upper traction	Holding (Traction)	Catheter Seminal vesicles (SV)	Grasper	R.6.4.1	Identify the Catheter and the SV		
							R.6.4.2	Identify the region of the Catheter and the SV to be grasped together		
							R.6.4.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target regions		
							R.6.4.4	Reach the target regions without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		
							R.6.4.5	Grasp the target regions		
							R.6.4.6	Plan the direction of the requested upper-traction		
R.6.4.7	Implement and maintain the traction									
7	Vas deferens and arteries are exposed	1	Upper anterior traction on the peritoneum	Holding (Traction)	Peritoneum	Grasper	R.7.1.A.1	Identify the Peritoneum		
							R.7.1.A.2	Identify the region of the Peritoneum to be grasped		
							R.7.1.A.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region		
							R.7.1.A.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		
							R.7.1.A.5	Grasp the target region		
							R.7.1.A.6	Plan the direction of the requested upper-anterior traction		

D1.2 Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform

						R.7.1.A.7	Implement and maintain the traction			
			Suction and cleaning of blood	Suction	Smoke	Suction-irrigator	R.7.1.B.1	Identify the Peritoneum		
							R.7.1.B.2	Identify the region of the Peritoneum to be pushed		
							R.7.1.B.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region		
							R.7.1.B.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		
							R.7.1.B.5	Plan the direction for the upper traction		
							R.7.1.B.6	Implement and maintain the traction		
8	Division of vas deferens	1	The vas deferens are controlled using the clips	Putting Hemoclip /s	Vas deferens	Automatic Clip Applier	R.8.1.1	Identify the Vas deferens		
							R.8.1.2	Identify the region/s of the Vas deferens that are bleeding		
							R.8.1.3	Plan the trajectory/ies to reach the target regions		
							R.8.1.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		
							R.8.1.5	Plan the best location where to put the Hemoclip/s avoiding entrapping other anatomical structures		
							R.8.1.6	Put the Hem-o clip/s where planned		

D1.2 Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform

						R.8.1.7	Pull back the applier			
9	Exposure of the seminal vesicles	1	The fibrovascular tissue is controlled using the clips	Putting Hemoclip /s	Fibrovascular tissue (FT)	Automatic Clip Applier	R.9.1.1	Identify the Fibrovascular tissue (FT)		
							R.9.1.2	Identify the region/s of the Ft that are bleeding		
							R.9.1.3	Plan the trajectory/ies to reach the target regions		
							R.9.1.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		
							R.9.1.5	Plan the best location where to put the Hemoclip/s avoiding entrapping other anatomical structures		
							R.9.1.6	Put the Hem-o clip/s where planned		
							R.9.1.7	Pull back the applier		
		2	Upper traction of the seminal vesicles	Holding (Traction)	Seminal vesicles (SV)	Grasper	R.9.2.A.1	Identify the Seminal vesicles		
							R.9.2.A.2	Identify the region of the Seminal vesicles to be grasped		
							R.9.2.A.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region		
							R.9.2.A.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		
							R.9.2.A.5	Grasp the target region		
							R.9.2.A.6	Plan the direction of the requested upper traction		
							R.9.2.A.7	Implement and maintain the traction		

D1.2 Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform

			The seminal vesicles are controlled using the clips	Putting Hemoclip /s	Seminal vesicles (SV)	Automatic Clip Applier	R.9.2.B.1	Identify the Seminal vesicles (SV)		
							R.9.2.B.2	Plan the trajectory/ies to reach the Seminal vesicles		
							R.9.2.B.3	Reach the Sv without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		
							R.9.2.B.4	Plan the best location where to put the Hemoclip/s avoiding entrapping other anatomical structures		
							R.9.2.B.5	Put the Hemo clip/s where planned		
							R.9.2.B.6	Pull back the applier		
		3	The seminal vesicle is grasped to help liberate the posterior avascular plane.	Holding (Traction)	Seminal vesicle (SV)	Grasper	R.9.3.1	Identify the Seminal vesicles		
							R.9.3.2	Identify the region of the Seminal vesicles to be grasped		
							R.9.3.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region/s		
							R.9.3.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		
							R.9.3.5	Grasp the target region		
							R.9.3.6	Plan the direction of the requested counter-traction		
							R.9.3.7	Implement and maintain the traction		
11	Urethral division	1	Traction/ Suction and cleaning blood	Traction / Suction	Urethra / Blood	Suction-irrigator	R.11.1.1	Identify the Urethra		
							R.11.1.2	Identify the region of the Urethra to be moved		

D1.2 Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform

						R.11.1.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region			
						R.11.1.4	Reach the target region without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments			
						R.11.1.5	Plan the direction for the upper traction			
						R.11.1.6	Implement and maintain the traction			
		2	Seminal vesicles are collectively grasped	Holding (Traction)	Seminal vesicle (SV)	Grasper	R.11.2.A.1	Identify the SV		
	R.11.2.A.2						Identify the region of SV to be grasped			
	R.11.2.A.3						Plan the trajectory to reach the target region			
	R.11.2.A.4						Reach the target regions without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments			
	R.11.2.A.5						Grasp the target region			
	R.11.2.A.6						Plan the direction of the requested traction			
	R.11.2.A.7						Implement and maintain the traction			
		Suction and cleaning of smoke and blood	Suction	Blood	Suction-irrigator	R.11.2.B.1	Identify the bleeding/smoke			
	R.11.2.B.2					Plan the trajectory to reach the target bleeding region/smoke				

D1.2 Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform

						R.11.2.B.3	Reach the target regions without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments			
						R.11.2.B.4	Suck the blood/smoke until the surgical working space is clear			
13	Vesicoureteral anastomosis	1	The assistant passes the needle and the suture thread to the surgeon	Holding (Needles)	Needle/s	Grasper	R.13.1.1	Identify the surgical needle + thread and the da Vinci needle holder		
							R.13.1.2	Identify the region of the needle to be grasped		
							R.13.1.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the da Vinci needle holder		
							R.13.1.4	Reach the da Vinci needle holder without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		
							R.13.1.5	Keep on holding the surgical needle and wait for the da Vinci needle holder to grab it		
							R.13.1.6	Release the surgical needle		
		3	The assistant cuts the suture's thread	Cutting	Suture's thread	Scissor	R.13.3.A.1	Identify the surgical thread and the da Vinci needle holder		
							R.13.3.A.2	Identify the region of the thread to be cut		
							R.13.3.A.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the target region of the thread		
							R.13.3.A.4	Reach it without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		
R.13.3.A.5	Cut the tread									

D1.2 Experimental tests and validation activities on the MULTIROBOTS-SURGERY platform

			The needles can be snapped out and removed from the body	Holding (Needles)	Needle/s	Grasper	R.13.3.B.1	Identify the surgical needle + thread and the da Vinci needle holder		
							R.13.3.B.2	Identify the region of the needle to be grasped		
							R.13.3.B.3	Plan the trajectory to reach the surgical needle		
							R.13.3.B.4	Reach the needle without colliding critical anatomical structures and/or other instruments		
							R.13.3.B.5	Grasp the needle		
							R.13.3.B.6	Plan the path to take it out from the surgical workspace		
							R.13.3.B.7	Take the needle out from the surgical workspace		

11 Appendix III – SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform evaluation questionnaires

Appendix III includes the survey developed in the project, to be proposed to surgeons for the assessment of usability and functionality factors related to MULTIROBOTS platform for surgeries. The participants will complete a brief questionnaire of background information. This would allow for statistical sample comparisons and differences in expertise, age, years of work etc.

CHARACTERISATION OF THE PARTICIPANTS' POOL:

Name:

Surname:

Experimental Code:

Age:

Hospital:

How many laparoscopic surgeries have you performed as first surgeon?

- 1-50
- 50-100
- >100

How many laparoscopic surgeries have you performed as assistant?

- 1-50
- 50-100
- >100

How many robotic-assisted surgeries have you performed as first surgeon?

- 1-50
- 50-100
- >100

How many robotic-assisted surgeries have you performed as assistant?

- 1-50
- 50-100
- >100

SARAS MULTIROBOTS PLATFORM QUALITATIVE ASSESSMENT QUESTIONNAIRE

Please, answer the items below by writing in the box at the end of each item the letter that best reflects your opinion.

1. Handling of instruments				
1	2	3	4	5
I was unable to translate my movements into robotic movements		I was able to translate my movements into basic robotic movements		I was clearly able to translate my movements into full robotic movements
2. Spatial awareness				
1	2	3	4	5
Able to made use of a single degree of freedom		Able to use multiple degrees of freedom		Able to use all degrees of freedom in maneuvering the robot
3. Time and motion				
1	2	3	4	5
Many unnecessary moves to reach the target		Efficient time/motion but some unnecessary moves to reach the target		Clear economy of movement and maximum efficiency to reach the target
4. Depth perception:				
1	2	3	4	5
Constantly overshoots target, wide swings, slow to correct		Some overshooting or missing of target, but quick to correct		Accurately directs instruments in correct plane to target
5. Bimanual dexterity:				
1	2	3	4	5
Poor coordination between the SARAS robotic arms		Not optimized interactions between the SARAS robotic arms		Optimized coordination between the SARAS robotic arms

6. Efficiency:				
1	2	3	4	5
Inefficient efforts; the task progression is discontinuous		Slow, but planned movements are reasonably organized		Fluid task progression
7. Force sensitivity (force feedback on manipulators):				
1	2	3	4	5
Rough moves, tears tissue, injures nearby structures, poor control		Quite smooth moves, reasonably good tissue handling, minor trauma to adjacent tissue		Smooth moves, application of appropriate tension, negligible injury to adjacent structures
8. Movement accuracy:				
1	2	3	4	5
Average maximum distance deviated from straight line > 20 mm	Average maximum distance deviated from straight line 15–19 mm	Average maximum distance deviated from straight line 10–14 mm	Average maximum distance deviated from straight line 5–9 mm	Average maximum distance deviated from straight line < 5 mm
9. Placement accuracy:				
1	2	3	4	5
Average maximum distance from final placement line > 20 mm	Average maximum distance from final placement line 15-19 mm	Average maximum distance from final placement line 10-14 mm	Average maximum distance from final placement line 5–9 mm	Average maximum distance from final placement line < 5 mm
10. Speed:				
1	2	3	4	5
Slowest completed interface		Intermediate completed interface		Fastest completed interface

SARAS MULTIROBOTS PLATFORM USABILITY QUESTIONNAIRE

Please, answer the items below by writing in the box at the end of each item the letter that best reflects your opinion.

A	B	C	D	E
Strongly Disagree	Disagree Slightly	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree

1. The quality of the overall experience was good	A	B	C	D	E
	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2. The surgical movements were translated accurately by the robotic platform	A	B	C	D	E
	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3. The robotic surgical arms moved responsively	A	B	C	D	E
	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4. The robotic platform was adequate in completing the tasks	A	B	C	D	E
	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5. The status of the robotic platform is always clear	A	B	C	D	E
	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6. The visual equipment is helpful and appropriate	A	B	C	D	E
	<input type="checkbox"/>				
7. The actions of the robotic platform match actions performed by the user (i.e.: time delay, direction of motions, depth perception...)	A	B	C	D	E
	<input type="checkbox"/>				
8. The robotic platform allows to recover from errors consistently	A	B	C	D	E
	<input type="checkbox"/>				
9. The operator of the robotic platform is always in control of any tasks or actions in the process	A	B	C	D	E
	<input type="checkbox"/>				
10. The robotic platform does not contain unnecessary or misleading information	A	B	C	D	E
	<input type="checkbox"/>				

11. There is enough guidance/support to reduce the effort for the users	A	B	C	D	E
	<input type="checkbox"/>				
12. The situations (actions, messages, feedbacks) presented by the robotic platform are clear and self explanatory	A	B	C	D	E
	<input type="checkbox"/>				
13. All the provided guidance/ support information is useful and easy to understand	A	B	C	D	E
	<input type="checkbox"/>				
14. The information provided by the robotic platform is easy to understand	A	B	C	D	E
	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Have you experienced any relevant usability problem while operating the robotic platform?

(yes) (no)

If Yes, please expand below:

SARAS COMMUNICATION AND COORDINATION QUESTIONNAIRE - FIRST SURGEON

Please, answer the items below by writing in the box at the end of each item the letter that best reflects your opinion.

Communication skills:				
1	2	3	4	5
I had frequent problems of coordination between the surgeons or difficulties to communicate		I had appropriate communication/coordination between the surgeons most of the time		I had good communication/coordination between the surgeons at all times

A	B	C	D	E
Strongly Disagree	Disagree Slightly	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree

1. I was able communicate effectively	A B C D E
	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
2. I felt staff able to understand my questions and comments	A B C D E
	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
1. I felt comfortable communicating with staff from my telesurgery location	A B C D E
	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
2. I was able to hear clinical information and exchanges clearly	A B C D E
	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>

SARAS COMMUNICATION AND COORDINATION QUESTIONNAIRE – ASSISTANT SURGEON

Please, answer the items below by writing in the box at the end of each item the letter that best reflects your opinion.

Communication skills:				
1	2	3	4	5
I had frequent problems of coordination between the surgeons or difficulties to communicate		I had appropriate communication/coordination between the surgeons most of the time		I had good communication/coordination between the surgeons at all times

A	B	C	D	E
Strongly Disagree	Disagree Slightly	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree

3. I was able communicate effectively	A	B	C	D	E
	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4. remote physician able to understand my questions and comments	A	B	C	D	E
	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5. I felt comfortable communicating with the first surgeon	A	B	C	D	E
	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6. I was able to hear remote clinical communications clearly	A	B	C	D	E
	<input type="checkbox"/>				

12 Appendix IV – SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform questionnaires results

12.1 Results of SARAS MULTIROBOTS platform Qualitative Assessment Questionnaire

	SURG1	SURG2	SURG3	SURG4
1. Handling of instruments	4	3	2	4
2. Spatial awareness	4	2	2	4
3. Time and motion	3	3	1	4
4. Depth perception	3	2	2	2
5. Bimanual dexterity	4	3	3	3
6. Efficiency	4	2	1	3
7. Force sensitivity (force feedback on manipulators)	3	2	2	2
8. Movement accuracy	3	2	2	4
9. Placement accuracy	3	3	2	4
10. Speed	3	2	2	3

12.2 Results of SARAS Usability Questionnaire

	SURG1	SURG2	SURG3	SURG4
1. The quality of the overall experience was good	4	3	3	4
2. The surgical movements were translated accurately by the robotic platform	3	2	2	3
3. The robotic surgical arms moved responsively	3	2	2	4
4. The robotic platform was adequate in completing the tasks	3	2	1	3
5. The status of the robotic platform is always clear	3	1	2	4
6. The visual equipment is helpful and appropriate	4	1	3	2
7. The actions of the robotic platform match actions performed by the user (i.e.: time delay, direction of motion, depth perception...)	3	2	3	2
8. The robotic platform allows to recover from errors consistently	3	2	2	2
9. The operator of the robotic platform is always in control of any tasks or actions in the process	2	1	2	3
10. The robotic platform does not contain unnecessary or misleading information	3	2	2	3

11. There is enough guidance/support to reduce the effort for the users	3	1	2	2
12. The situation (actions, messages, feedbacks) presented by the robotic platform are clear and self explanatory	2	1	3	4
13. All the provided guidance/support information is useful and easy to understand	3	2	2	3
14. The information provided by the robotic platform is easy to understand	3	2	2	4

12.3 Results of Communication and Coordination questionnaire - first surgeon and assistant

	SURG1	SURG2		SURG3		SURG4
	Main Surgeon	Main Surgeon	Assistant	Main Surgeon	Assistant	Main Surgeon
Communication skills	3	4	4	0	2	4
1. I was able communicate effectively	3	5	5	0	2	3
2. I felt staff/remote physician able to understand my questions and comments	3	5	5	0	2	4
3. I felt comfortable communicating with staff from my telesurgery location	3	5	5	0	2	4
4. I was able to hear clinical information and exchanges clearly	3	5	5	0	2	4